

Conference Abstract

Genetic diversity of *Misgurnus fossilis* in Austria

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Abstract

The weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*, L., 1758) is a species of the Cobitidae family. It is a small, benthic fish that feeds mostly on aquatic invertebrates and some detritus (Lelek 1987). Its native distribution area extends from the Meuse drainage basin in France to the Volga drainage basin in Russia (Kottelat and Freyhof 2007). However, it is highly specialised to habitats in floodplain waters and ditches, and has low dispersal ability (Meyer and Hinrichs 2000, Schauer et al. 2013, Schreiber et al. 2018). This leads to strong population fragmentation and often results in regional extinction (Hartvich et al. 2010). Previous studies have shown that *M. fossilis* exhibits low genetic diversity, which may be explained by the recent dispersal of a bottlenecked population from a single refuge after the last glaciation (Bohlen et al. 2007; Mendel et al. 2008). This study (for the Power Point presentation see the Suppl. material 1) analysed barcoding region of cytochrome oxidase I (COI) of 30 specimens in several populations of *M. fossilis* throughout its distribution range in Austria (Fig. 1). However, most of the sequences were found to be identical (Fig. 1, marked in red circles), with five exhibiting one or two mutations differences (Fig. 1, marked with different colours). These results, in accordance with previous studies, demonstrate that *M. fossilis* in Austria exhibits low genetic diversity

at the mitochondrial DNA level, which may increase its vulnerability to rapid habitat changes.

Figure 1. [doi](#)

Distribution of analysed specimens of *Misgurnus fossilis* in Austria. The results of the analysis of the barcoding region of cytochrome oxidase I (COI) of 30 specimens are presented. The most common haplotype is shown in red. Unique haplotypes, only represented in one specimen each are marked with other colours, green, light blue, dark blue, brown and yellow.

Keywords

Barcoding, COI, low genetic diversity

Presenting author

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Ethics and security

The fish were caught under the permission of the concerned state, federal, or private agencies and institutions and in accordance with the Austrian state laws on fisheries.

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Genetic diversity of *Misgurnus fossilis* in Austria [doi](#)

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